

Knowledge Regarding Uterine Cancer among Reproductive Age Women

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ABSTRACT

Cancer is a disease in which abnormal cells divide without control and are able to invade other tissues. Uterine cancer is the most common cancer occurring in reproductive system of women. Uterine cancer begins when healthy cells in the uterus change and grow out of control, forming a mass of cells called a tumour. The aim of the study is to identify the knowledge regarding uterine cancer among reproductive age women. The objective of the study is to assess the knowledge regarding uterine cancer among reproductive age women and to find the association between socio demographic variables and knowledge regarding uterine cancer. In this study Quantitative research design was used to assess the knowledge among reproductive age women in selected villages of Distt. Roopnagar. 100 Reproductive age women were taken as a sample and Structured interview questionnaire was used for data collection. The results of the study states that 78% of women had average knowledge, 20% of women had good knowledge and remaining 2% had poor knowledge regarding uterine cancer and the Mean±SD of knowledge score was 12.66±2.23. There is significant association between knowledge and selected socio demographic variables as $p < 0.05$. Study concluded that majority of women had average knowledge so there is need to enhance the knowledge regarding uterine cancer by educating the women.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge, Uterine cancer, reproductive age women

I. INTRODUCTION:

Cancer is a leading cause of death worldwide and accounted for 7.6 million deaths around 13% of deaths occur in 2008. Worldwide deaths from cancer are projected to continue to rise over 13.1 million in 2030. According to national cancer registry program of the India council of medical research (ICMR) more than 1300 Indians die every day due to cancer.

Uterine cancer is the most common cancer occurring in a woman's reproductive system. Uterine cancer begins when healthy cells in the uterus change and grow out of control, forming a mass of cells called tumor. A tumor can be cancerous or benign. A cancerous tumor is malignant, as it can grow and spread to other parts of the body. A benign tumor can grow but generally will not invade other tissues. Noncancerous conditions of the uterus include such as: Fibroids: Benign tumors in the muscle of the uterus. Benign polyps: Abnormal growths in the lining of the uterus. Endometriosis: A condition in which endometrial tissue, which usually the inside of the uterus, is found on the outside of the uterus or other organs. Endometrial hyperplasia: A condition in which there is an increased number of cells and glandular structures in the uterine lining.

1.1. NEED FOR THE STUDY

Endometrial cancer is the 15th most common cancer worldwide. There were over 380000 new cases in 2018. Study was conducted on Prevalence, Characteristics, and Risk Factors of Occult Uterine Cancer in Presumed Benign

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Hysterectomy and result of the study showed that 0.96% (95% confidence women age 18-29 years to 4.40% in women age ≥ 75 years; and varied from 0.14% in women undergoing hysterectomy for endometriosis to 0.62% for uterine fibroids and 8.43% for postmenopausal bleeding).

The risk of occult uterine cancer was also significantly associated with interval of the women had occult uterine cancer, including 0.75% with endometrial carcinoma and 0.22% with uterine sarcoma. The prevalence of leiomyosarcoma was 0.15%. Seventy-one percent of the endometrial carcinomas and 58.0% of the uterine sarcomas were at localized stage.

1.2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

A study to assess the knowledge regarding uterine cancer among reproductive age women residing in the selected villages of District Roopnagar, Punjab.

1.3. AIM

➤ To identify the knowledge regarding uterine cancer among reproductive age women.

1.4. OBJECTIVES

➤ To assess the knowledge regarding uterine cancer among reproductive age group women.
➤ To find the association between socio-demographic variables and knowledge regarding uterine cancer

1.5. ASSUMPTION

- The Reproductive age women may have some knowledge about uterine cancer.

1.6. DELIMITATION

- This is delimited to selected villages of district Roopnagar.

II. METHODOLOGY

The research design used in the study was non experimental descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted at selected villages of Distt. Roopnagar i.e.

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Table related to demographic variables of reproductive age women

Dhianapura, Chitamala. The sample was 100 reproductive age women were selected by convenient sampling technique. The tool used for the study was structured interviewed questionnaire section A description of the socio demographic characteristics of the study participants (demographic data such as age, education, marital status, monthly family income, occupation, religion), and section B related to structured interviewed questionnaire related to causes and risk factors, sign and symptoms, treatment and prevention of uterine cancer. Section c was related to association between selected socio demographic variables and knowledge regarding uterine cancer.

Table1 Distribution of study subjects as per their socio demographic variables N=100

S. No	Socio-demographic variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
01	Age		
	A. 15-25	24	24%
	B. 26-35	39	39%
	C. 36-45	27	27%
02	D. >45	10	10%
	Income		
	A. <5000	22	22%
	B. 5001-10000	48	48%
03	C. 10001-15000	19	19%
	D. >15001	11	11%
	Education		
	A. No formal education	11	11%
04	B. Primary education	30	30%
	C. Secondary education	43	43%
	D. Graduation and above	8	8%
	Marital status		
05	A. Unmarried	34	34%
	B. Married	60	60%
	C. Widow	6	6%
	D. Divorce	0	0%
06	Religion		
	A. Hindu	43	43%
	B. Muslim	1	1%
	C. Sikh	56	56%
07	D. Other	0	0%
	Occupation		
	A. Homemaker	69	69%
	B. Student	20	20%
08	C. Government employee	1	1%
	D. Private employee	10	10%

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE 3.1

The demographic characteristics revealed that 39% of people were in the age group of 26-35, 48% of people had monthly income 5001-10000, 43% underwent secondary education. Majority of 60% women were married, 56% of women were Sikh, 69% were homemaker.

3.2. Scoring of knowledge level of reproductive age women regarding uterine cancer N=100

Level of knowledge	Percentage	Frequency	Mean±SD
Poor(0-7)	2%	2	12.66±2.23
Average(8-14)	78%	78	
Good(>15)	20%	20	

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE 3.2

This table represents the level of knowledge of women at good and poor level of knowledge. Majority of 78% women had average knowledge regarding uterine cancer. Mean score and standard deviation of knowledge score is $M \pm SD$ 12.66 \pm 2.23.

3.3. Related to association between socio-demographic variables and knowledge regarding uterine cancer N=100

Sr. no	Sample characteristic	Good	Average	Poor	Chi square	df	p - value
01	Age						
	15-25	5	18	1	17.040	3	0.01**
	26-35	8	31	0			
	36-45	4	23	0			
	>45	3	6	1			
02	Income						
	<5000	4	17	1	30.800	3	0.000**
	5001-10000	10	37	1			
	10001-15000	5	14	0			
	>15000	1	10	0			
03	Education						
	No formal education	3	8	0	39.120	3	0.000**
	Primary education	5	32	1			
	Secondary education	11	32	0			
	Graduation and above	1	6	1			
04	Marital status						
	Unmarried	2	31	1	43.760	2	0.000**
	Married	17	43	0			
	Widow	1	4	1			
	Divorce	0	0	0			
05	Religion						
	Hindu	9	34	0	49.580	2	0.000**
	Muslim	1	0	0			
	Sikh	10	44	2			
	Other	0	0	0			
06	Occupation						
	Homemaker	15	52	2	110.480	3	0.000**
	Student	2	18	0			
	Govt. employee	0	1	0			
	Private employee	3	7	0			

Significant at $p < 0.05$ level

The data in the table reveals that there is significant association between knowledge and socio demographic variables i.e. age, income, education, marital status, religion and occupation as $p < 0.05$.

IV. NURSING IMPLICATIONS

- Nurses should be skilled enough in identifying, exploring and managing the problems faced by patients of uterine cancer.
- The nursing curriculum should have detailed topic on uterine cancer. The student when posted in maternity wards, hospital, and community should be able to give education to the women regarding the uterine cancer.
- The nursing student should be made aware of their responsibility to educate women regarding uterine cancer.
- The study findings can be effectively utilized by the emerging researchers for their references purpose.
- It is essential for nursing administration to facilitate public awareness program to improve the knowledge regarding uterine cancer among reproductive age women.
- The nursing administrator should implement the outreach programme to make the reproductive age women aware about the knowledge of uterine cancer by workshops, seminar etc.

V. CONCLUSION

Study concluded that the majority of women i.e. 78% had average knowledge regarding uterine cancer, 20% had good knowledge and the remaining 2% had poor knowledge regarding uterine cancer. Mean \pm SD was 12.66 \pm 2.23 of the study. There is need to enhance the knowledge of women which can prevent the future occurrence cases and also decrease the mortality and morbidity rates.

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